

TECHNIQUES FOR DEVELOPING EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS USING GAME TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: in this thesis, scientific opinions and recommendations on development techniques using game technologies in primary education are described.

Key words: diagnostics, primary education, educational system, game technologies, analysis, reproductive activity, pedagogical activity.

Introduction:

The primary school reflects all modern trends in pedagogy. It should be noted that the educational process is not only a collection of subjects, but also a unity of the functions of teaching, developing and educating schoolchildren in the process of learning each subject. The school should not serve as a distribution point, a storehouse of ready-made knowledge, skills and competences - this is not relevant today. A modern elementary school should form a person who can make decisions independently and find ways to implement them using creativity in their actions. The school should solve the new problems facing the Russian education, first of all, the conditions should be observed for the development of the child as a subject of his activity, not the object of the teacher's pedagogical influence, but the subject of development. should be. To implement such high-quality education, game techniques that help to effectively reveal children's abilities and their potential can serve, because information is presented in a playful way, and this type of activity can be used in various lessons, to which young attracts students.

How to organize a lesson, fulfilling all the requirements of the standards of the state educational standard? It is important that we understand what the criteria for the effectiveness of the lesson, built within the framework of the federal state educational standard, should be:

- ❖ The goals of the lesson are determined by the tendency to transfer the function from the teacher to the student.
- ❖ The teacher regularly teaches children to practice reflexive action - the child can assess his capabilities, readiness for the lesson, identify ignorance, and also find the causes of difficulties.

- ❖ Various forms, methods and methods of teaching are used, game technologies are the most clearly expressed to increase the level of activity of students in the educational process.
- ❖ The teacher has dialogue technology, teaches students to act and ask questions.
- ❖ The teacher effectively combines reproductive and problematic forms of education, teaches children to work according to rules and creatively.
- ❖ In the lesson, there are specific criteria for tasks and self-control and self-evaluation - at this stage, there is a special formation of control and evaluation activities among students.
- ❖ The teacher tries to understand all educational materials by all students using special methods.
- ❖ The teacher strives to assess the real progress of each student, encouraging and supporting even the smallest achievements.
- ❖ The teacher specially plans the communicative tasks of the lesson.
- ❖ The teacher accepts and encourages a personal position expressed by the student, teaches a different opinion, specific forms of their expression.
- ❖ The style, the tone of relations established in the lesson creates an atmosphere of cooperation, cooperation, psychological comfort.
- ❖ The lesson has a deep personal influence "learning teacher" - this happens through relationships, joint activities, etc.

Also, you need to know the structure of the lesson and its structural elements and types in order to properly incorporate various game techniques into the students' work. The structure of the lesson is a set of different options of interaction between the elements of the lesson that occurs in the educational process and ensures its targeted effectiveness.

The main stages of the lesson include:

- Organizational moment.
- Homework Check Phase. Knowledge, skill test phase and skills, homework test at this phase of the lesson can be assigned to children through game control activities. Using games such as "I am a teacher", "supervisor", students independently check the work done by someone.
- The stage of preparing students for active and conscious assimilation of new material.
- The stage of acquiring new knowledge and methods of action.

Phase of initial verification of learned understanding, at this stage, game activities that hide complex mental activity and make it more interesting are perfect. For example, students name the subject shown in the picture, listen to the sound of the word and determine whether the studied sound is present in it, and then place this picture in a house of a certain color.

Stage of integration of new material, you can use it game methodology - comparing the letter with the image of familiar objects, thus students will remember the spelling of the given letter faster.

- ❖ Stage of application of knowledge and action methods.
- ❖ Stage of generalization and systematization of knowledge.
- ❖ The stage of control and self-regulation of knowledge and action methods.
- ❖ Stage of correction of knowledge and methods of action.
- ❖ The stage of informing students about homework and briefing is during its implementation.
- ❖ Reflection and evaluation phase. Summary of the lesson.

Lessons are classified according to the didactic purpose, the organization of the lessons, as well as the content and methods of the lesson. Didactic tasks to be solved in the lesson, teaching methods and organization of students' educational activities are also considered. Studying the essence and structure of the lesson leads to the conclusion that the lesson is a complex pedagogical object. Like any complex object, classes can be divided into types according to various characteristics. As examples of such typologies, which divide lessons according to the form of their delivery, the following can be cited:

1. *Lessons in the form of competitions and games: competition, tournament, relay, business game, role-playing game, crossword, quiz.*
2. *Lessons based on known forms, genres and working methods of social practice: brainstorming, interview, reportage, review.*
3. *Lessons reminding the forms of public communication: discussion, press conference, briefing, auction, regulated discussion, telemost.*
4. *Lessons based on fantasy: fairy tale lesson, unexpected lesson.*
5. *Lessons and organizations based on imitation of the activities of institutions: investigation, patent office, scientific council.*

This typology of lessons includes elements of game techniques, so we can say with confidence that the inclusion of a game or a game situation in the educational process helps to make one or another generalization, to understand the rules that have just been learned. , allows to consolidate or repeat the

knowledge acquired in the system. in new connections, it helps to master the material more deeply.

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